

ASSEMBLY OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE PARTS FOR THE EAGLET RUDDER USING WELDING TECHNIQUES

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SUMMARY: The purpose of this paper is to give information on the assembly of thermoplastic composite parts for a movable. The bonding techniques are first discussed in general and then more in detail the tooling to apply the techniques is discussed. In addition, the restrictions of each process regarding this assembly are mentioned.

KEYWORDS: thermoplastic composites, welding, assembly, tooling, rudder, skin, ribs.

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic composites are being used for their cost efficient process; one of these processes is rubber forming. Rubber forming is used to form parts for a thermoplastic composite rudder for the Eaglet, a full-composite 2-seater aircraft (figure 1).

The rudder of the Eaglet was redesigned from a thermo set sandwich structure to a thermoplastic multi-rib structure. This leads to a weight reduction of approximately 20 to 40%.

Figure 1: Eaglet aircraft, the rudder is encircled

Figure 2: exploded view of the rudder

The multi-rib concept consists of a skin, seven ribs, spar, leading edge and some caps and ribs to close the structure (see figure 2). The skin was thermo folded, the ribs, spar, leading edge and some of the closing ribs were rubber formed, and the lower end cap was both rubber formed and infused with RIM technology. All parts were assembled by using both resistance and ultrasonic welding. The material used to produce the rudder was continuous carbon fiber reinforced PEI (5H satin weave) from Ten Cate Advanced Composites (Cetex), with a lay-up

of $\pm 45; 0/90; \pm 45$, so 3 layers with a total thickness of 0,9 mm. The forming of the parts is described in [1] and in this paper the assembly process is described.

ASSEMBLY MOLD & ASSEMBLY SEQUENCE

The rudder is assembled in a negative mold (figure 3), which has the exact outer shape of the rudder. Since the tolerances have to be on the outer surface consequently, the rudder is assembled from the outside to the inside.

The order in which the parts are placed is important because of the limited accessibility of the rudder. An inconvenient order leads to a structure impossible to assemble. This must be taken into account when making the design. In this case, it meant an interactive process between the design engineer and the assembly engineer.

Figure 3: Assembly mold

WELDING TECHNIQUES

In this technology demonstrator two different welding techniques are used: resistance welding and ultrasonic welding. Joints longer than 50 mm are made using the resistance welding process (figure 4). Resistance welding uses an electrical current flowing through a conductive material to heat the interface of the joint. This heat is used to melt the thermoplastic interfaces, under a certain amount of pressure the interfaces fuse together, and after cooling a bond is created. The conductor, in this case a stainless steel mesh, remains in the bond. The metal mesh is embedded with the same matrix as used in the composite prior to welding, this to prevent voids in the bond.

Figure 4: Principle resistance welding

At the start of the project, all joints were intended to be made through resistance welding, but due to limitations of available space in the rudder a different process was needed. Conveniently, ultrasonic welding was already researched by our department and could be implemented.

The small ribs to spar joints are made with the ultrasonic welding process (figure 5). An ultrasonic welding machine generates ultrasonic vibrations. These vibrations are led to the bond through a horn, the vibrations generate heat at the interface causing it to melt. Under pressure the interfaces fuse and after cooling a bond is created.

Figure 5: Principle of ultrasonic welding

TOOLING FOR RESISTANCE WELDING

The tooling for resistance welding must provide the following functions:

- Positioning of the part.
- Providing pressure on the weld zone.
- Positioning and pressurizing the electrodes.

After several tests with different pressurizing systems an inflatable tube proved the most controllable. This tube is placed around a metal mold and into the part. After attaching the electrodes and the heating elements the whole set up is placed into the structure. By inflating the tube a controllable weld pressure is created. In figure 6 an example is shown of how the tube presses the weld zone and the electrodes. Also visible is the heating element, the mesh is only filled with thermoplastic material where a bond line is required.

Figure 6: Tooling for resistance welding of the ribs

The tooling for the spar (figure 7) is similar to those of the ribs except for the shape, again the spar is positioned and welded using the same system used for the welding of the ribs.

Figure 7: Tooling for welding of the spar

As mentioned before the rudder is constructed from a carbon fiber based composite. Carbon fiber is an electrically conductive material, so without any precautions the electrical current of the resistance welding will short circuit through the laminate. This phenomenon is highly undesired, as the laminate will locally reach high temperatures causing the matrix to burn. After such an event, the structure is lost. To prevent this from happening the metal mesh is electrically insulated with a coating able to withstand the high welding temperatures. In addition, special care has to be given to the electrodes; direct contact between them and the laminate has to be prevented. Figure 8 shows a detailed section of a successful weld of the largest rib. Notice that the outside of the skin is hardly affected by the temperatures of the weld process. With this technique, welds of several meters long can be made. A limitation is that small bonds are difficult to make because there is always an amount of space needed to place the electrodes

Figure 8: Details resistance welded bonds

TOOLING FOR ULTRASONIC WELDING

The ultrasonic welding machine had to be customized in order to weld the rib to spar bonds (figure 9). An additional support was added to the side of the welding machine. This is needed to prevent the welding forces of the horn crushing the structure. A hole in the spar is created to give access to the support.

Figure 9: base of ultrasonic welding machine with additional support

Ultrasonic welding is a very fast technique: the whole process takes place in a few seconds. In figure 10 an example of a rib-spar bond is shown. Notice the squeeze flow of resin out of the bond area. The limitations of this process are that only small sized bonds can be made and the bond must be accessible for the support tooling.

Figure 10: Detail of an ultrasonic welded bond

CONCLUSION

It is possible to assemble a thermoplastic composite based rudder using welding techniques. When using these technologies the design of the rudder has to be adjusted. With these technologies, the assembly time can be significantly reduced. To use all advantages of thermoplastic composites it is essential that the design of the structure is adjusted to really use the thermoplastic properties of the material. This demonstrator shows the problems creating a small structure, creating a bigger structure will solve problems regarding space while problems regarding scaling up of the bonding techniques might arise.

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